

Human Space Flight Docking Interoperability

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1.0 Introduction

For many years, space faring nations have defined and implemented docking systems that have met the needs and constraints of their own programs. The American *Gemini* and *Apollo* programs in the 1960's developed docking mechanisms specific to lunar missions. The Russian *Salyut*, *Soyuz* and later *Mir* programs developed docking mechanisms that were specific to docking and mating of spacecraft in low earth orbit.

*Apollo Command Module
and Lunar Lander mated*

*Russian Probe/Cone Docking Mechanism
on Soyuz spacecraft*

In over 40 years of human spaceflight, there have been only three programs that have brought together two or more nations in docking spacecraft in-flight; the *Apollo-Soyuz*

Test Program, the *Shuttle-Mir* Program and the *International Space Station Program (ISS)*. Each of these programs has relied on heritage docking mechanisms that were originally designed for previous missions. Of these programs, the only jointly developed docking mechanism was flown on the *Apollo-Soyuz Test Program* which was flown once.

Apollo-Soyuz Test Program

The majority of docking operations have been conducted by the Russian and American space agencies. To-date the Russians have had approximately 268 dockings while the Americans have had approximately 67.

Russian Salyut and Soyuz Spacecraft

Russian Androgynous Peripheral Assembly
With the recent successful flight of the European *Automated Transfer Vehicle (ATV)* to the *ISS*, Europe has completed their first docking operation. Recently the Chinese have announced plans for docking spacecraft in low earth orbit as well.

ATV Docking with ISS utilizing Probe/Cone

Based on the joint experience NASA has had with international partners and a desire to conduct future joint international missions,

Shuttle Docking with ISS utilizing Russian provided APAS

National Aeronautics and Space Administrations (NASA) has initiated efforts to form an international consensus on space exploration including missions to the moon, NASA has begun discussions concerning an international standard for docking spacecraft with its current International Space Station (ISS) Partners including the Russia Space Agency, Japanese Space Agency, Canada Space Agency and the European Space Agency. Once a consensus is reached with its current human space flight partners, NASA intends to broaden the consensus to other space agencies. The end objective of these discussions is to formulate and agree upon a common docking interface definition that willing countries may design and build to if they choose to be compatible with other nation's human space flight spacecraft.

2.0 Missions

Though there are many aspects to docking two spacecraft in space such as proximity operations, rendezvous operations, target acquisition, communications, guidance and navigation, the standard will only address the necessary functions and performance parameters associated with the physical joining of two spacecraft. Other operational in-space considerations will not be addressed such as

Extra-Vehicular Activities (EVA), maintenance, redundancy, or failure scenarios.

Two scenarios that drive the extremes of such a standard are in the simplest case, the prospect of in-space human rescue, and in the most comprehensive case, the prospect of stronger cooperation in international contributions in future missions, such as space stations and exploration activities. The first scenario drives the minimum set of standards for structural

attachment. The second scenario drives a complete set of standards affecting fault-tolerant mating and un-mating, full pressurization, power, data, fluid, resupply, electrical bonding, and other concerns.

2.1 Crew Rescue

Similar to international submarine rescue capabilities, the minimum common functions and standards between national space programs may be derived from a rescue mission. Basic operations may include rendezvous between a disabled crewed vehicle and an active rescue vehicle. It can be conceived that such a mission would be time critical and would not be able to accommodate design or hardware changes in order to execute such a mission. Given the nature of an in-space rescue mission, two primary modes of operation can be conceived: first a "soft capture" to facilitate an Extra-Vehicular Activity (EVA) transfer of crew from the disabled spacecraft to the rescue spacecraft; and second, a "hard docking" that facilitates a pressurized transfer without the need to depressurize either spacecraft.

The first scenario, a soft capture, would require both spacecraft to accommodate depressurization capabilities as well as pressurized crew suits and the ability to transfer the crew from one spacecraft to another. If the soft capture were executed by a primary docking interface, an alternate crew egress and ingress would be required. This scenario assumes a free drift mode for both spacecraft while attached and therefore does not require active attitude control by either spacecraft while joined.

The second scenario, a hard docking, would facilitate the transfer of the crew from the disabled craft to the rescue spacecraft through a pressurized docking interface.

2.2 Docked Mission Operations

Docked mission operations can be characterized as two or more spacecraft physically mated together structurally supporting pressurized crew operations and joined maneuvers. This configuration implies at least two significant levels of integration; first, structural and thermal integrity to support attitude control, dynamic orbit adjustments and a habitable crew environment; and second, operations integration to providing power, data, fluids or other capabilities across the mated spacecraft to support mission operations and objectives.

3.0 Standard Parameters

The design and operation of a docking mechanism is driven by a set of parameters that define the physical and performance characteristics. These parameters may be defined for both the crew rescue and docked missions. Additionally, the parameters are also categorized into the two major operations of a docking mechanism; soft capture and hard dock. Soft capture is defined as the initial contact between two spacecraft where the forces and momentum of the two spacecraft are attenuated. Hard dock is defined as the structural joining of the two spacecraft.

3.1 Crew Rescue Mission

For a soft capture docking scenario for crew rescue where the objective is to transfer the crew from the disabled spacecraft to the rescue vehicle by EVA, the following parameters will drive the functional and performance requirements of the interface:

- capture ring diameter
- alignment guide configuration
- capture interface
- load limiting configuration
- capture indications

For soft capture release, the following parameters will apply:

- separation indication
- separation rates

For a hard docking, in addition to the soft capture parameters, the following parameters will apply:

- Hard docking ring diameter
- Pressure seal configuration
- Structural latching interface

- Fine alignment interface
- Interferences to docking

Parameters for undocking operations must also be considered:

- separation rates
- separation mechanisms
- separation indication

3.2 Docked Mission Operations

Parameters for docked mission operation must include the same parameters as for a rescue mission in addition to the following parameters:

- integrated structural and thermal integrity to perform mission
- power data interfaces
- grounding
- fluid interfaces
- hatch tunnel diameter
- manual overrides
- docking and pressure indications
- sequence timing

4.0 Moving Forward

NASA and its International Partners are currently conducting trade studies to determine the appropriate values and configurations for the above parameters. Teams are meeting regularly with the goal to develop a preliminary docking standard by year end or the beginning of next year. Once a preliminary understanding of a docking standard is reached, the result will be brought forward to the larger space community for discussion and possible acceptance of an international standard. NASA and its partners are also evaluating the appropriate international mechanisms to bring forward such an international standard.